

3R'S EVERY HOUR: UNMASKING THE VIEWS OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS TOWARDS PROPER WASTE MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

This study was geared to unmask the views of senior high school students towards proper waste management in a private institution in Pampanga, Philippines. The researchers interviewed 30 senior high school students who voluntarily participated by responding to an open-ended questionnaire. The findings of the open-ended questionnaire deciphered the views of the senior high school students towards proper waste management. This study utilized Braun and Clarke's Thematic analysis. The study revealed five emerging themes that described the views of the senior high school students towards proper waste management, namely: (1) Trash Breaks: Applying Intervals to Classroom Cleanup. (2) Inconsistent Commitment to Continuous Workplace Cleanliness. (3) Disciplinary Measures and Academic Consequences of Inadequate Trash Disposal. (4) Promoting responsible waste management and environmental initiatives (5) Educational Engagement and Behavior Adjustment About Proper Waste Management. The findings offer actionable insights for private institutions, recommending the initiation of eco-friendly programs and educational workshops to improve waste management practices.

Keywords: *3Rs, Senior High School Student, Waste management, School*

INTRODUCTION

Proper waste management presents a significant challenge globally, especially within educational institutions, where fostering responsible citizenship is a priority. The world generates over 2 billion tons of municipal solid waste annually, with a substantial portion ending up in landfills, incinerators, or polluting oceans and natural habitats. As populations grow, so does waste production due to increased consumption, packaging, and use of disposable items. In countries like the Philippines, inadequate waste management persists despite regulations lacking infrastructure, limited resources, and enforcement challenges, resulting in environmental degradation and health risks. Effective waste management is essential for a clean, healthy, and sustainable environment, particularly within educational settings, where students play a pivotal role in shaping sustainable behaviors. The World Bank's (2018) projection of global waste nearly doubling by 2050 underscores the urgent need for effective waste management practices. Students' perspectives on waste management in educational institutions are crucial for understanding and promoting sustainable behaviors, according to Reno (2015). However, despite efforts such as the "CLAYGO" policies, students still struggle with proper waste disposal, as noted by Owojori (2022). Current research lacks a comprehensive study of the impacts of allocating specific break times for teachers, during which students are given dedicated opportunities to properly dispose of their trash and waste materials.

Moreso, interventions are needed to address these challenges, focusing on shaping students' attitudes and perceptions toward waste management, as Owojori (2022) emphasized. Amasuomo and Baird (2015) highlights the importance of education in promoting proper waste disposal practices and increasing awareness. Addressing the gaps in waste management studies, particularly in basic education, is crucial, as highlighted by Bashir (2020). This study aims to fill these gaps by directly investigating student perspectives in private institutions. It seeks to understand student attitudes and behaviors towards the 3Rs (Reduce, Reuse, Recycle) and the factors influencing their participation through surveys and interviews. Additionally, the study aims to identify challenges and barriers hindering student participation, potentially revealing discrepancies between school policies and student practices. By involving the community and fostering a sense of shared responsibility, the researchers aim to contribute to building a sustainable future. To enhance waste management practices in schools, disciplinary measures for improper waste disposal among students are recommended. Allowing sufficient time for waste disposal in appropriate bins and organizing eco-friendly initiatives regularly can promote the principles of the 3Rs. Educating both schools and the public on the value of waste and its impact on the environment is also crucial, as suggested by Kumar et al (2017) implementing these measures can significantly improve waste management practices in educational institutions, contributing positively to the environment. The findings of this research paper aim to add insights to the existing literature on waste management and encourage students to take an active role in sustainability.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study is to unmask students' views towards proper waste management. Specifically, it seeks answers to the following questions:

1. What are the perceptions of students regarding proper waste management practices, including their understanding, attitudes, and behaviors toward waste disposal and recycling?
2. What challenges or barriers do senior high school students face in adopting and practicing the 3Rs (Reduce, Reuse, and Recycle) principles consistently throughout the school day?
3. How satisfied are students with the current waste management practices at the private institution located at San Fernando, Pampanga?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a qualitative research design to investigate the depth, richness, and complexity inherent in students' perceptions, opinions, and attitudes toward waste management practices. By employing qualitative methods, the researchers aim to capture the nuanced and multifaceted views of senior high school students regarding waste management, including reducing, reusing, and recycling practices. Previous research underscores the importance of understanding student perspectives on environmental initiatives within educational settings (Brown, 2020). Brown's (2020) study highlights that students' attitudes and behaviors toward waste management can significantly influence the success of such initiatives. To comprehend how students experience waste management in their schools, this study employed a phenomenological approach. This method, as described by Team (2023), prioritizes capturing the unique perspectives, beliefs, and feelings of students. It aims to go beyond data collection, seeking to grasp the subjective meaning students attach to waste management practices.

Meanwhile, the participants for this study were 30 senior high school students from a specific private institution, purposively selected based on specific criteria relevant to the research question. The focus was on students aged 15 to 18 years old, typically in Grades 11th and 12th, within this institution. Senior high school students represent a critical stage in developing environmental consciousness and personal responsibility (DeJonckheere, 2019). Participants of this study were chosen using purposive sampling technique. Purposive sampling, as described by Arikunto (2014), involves selecting samples based on specific objectives rather than random selection. With purposive sampling, the researcher selected participants based on the needs and goals of the study. The use of purposive sampling in this study is appropriate because it allows the researcher to establish specific criteria for selecting potential participants. For this study, semi-structured interviews were conducted with senior high school students to explore their views on proper waste management. This method balances flexibility and structure, allowing for in-depth exploration of predetermined themes while permitting participants to

express their perspectives freely. Before each interview, the researchers ensure informed consent and schedule sessions in private settings to create a comfortable environment. Using open-ended questions, the researchers discussed students' perceptions, experiences, challenges, and suggestions regarding waste management practices within their school environment (Nandan, 2017). The information obtained from the participants' feedback was systematically collected, transcribed, arranged, scrutinized, and interpreted to draw meaningful insights, employing Braun and Clarke's (2006) thematic analysis approach. According to Braun and Clarke (2006), this method is frequently used in qualitative research because it provides insightful and comprehensive findings. These key steps include "familiarization, coding the data, generating initial themes, reviewing the themes, naming and defining the themes, and writing up the report."

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Theme 1: Trash Breaks: Applying Intervals to Classroom Cleanup.

In the bustling atmosphere of classrooms, where curiosity fuels learning and collaboration, the importance of cleanliness often fades into the background amid ongoing discussions. However, it's vital to acknowledge that implementing "trash breaks" is essential. Cluttered spaces can impede collaborative learning, while disorganization and a lack of hygiene can cause discomfort and stress, disrupting student focus and motivation. Neglected classrooms may even suggest an indifference toward the learning environment, shaping students' perceptions of school and their educational journey. Therefore, integrating "Trash Breaks" emerges as a practical solution to effectively address these challenges. Mian et al. (2017) highlights that the physical condition of both home and school environments reflects students' attitudes towards their surroundings. A cleaning rota, particularly beneficial for primary school students, as proposed by the Fidelis Group, assigns each student a day to tidy the classroom, fostering a sense of responsibility for maintaining a conducive learning space. Moreover, the authority of the teacher within the classroom is paramount in initiating such initiatives. Debrah (2020) emphasizes that teachers' knowledge and awareness play a crucial role in promoting sustainable education and environmental sustainability goals. Sacrificing just five minutes of class time for a trash break, led by the teacher, can significantly contribute to maintaining a clean and organized learning environment, while also instilling in students the importance of environmental responsibility.

Subtheme 1.1: Empowering Teachers as Environmental Stewards

Within the classroom environment, teachers wield significant influence not only in imparting knowledge but also in shaping students' attitudes toward their surroundings. By taking proactive steps such as initiating "Trash Breaks," teachers can actively foster environmental stewardship among students. According to Joshi and Ahmed (2016), teachers play a pivotal role in shaping the lives of their students, influencing not only their

academic development but also their personal growth and character formation. Beyond the classroom, teachers often serve as mentors, guides, and role models, leaving an indelible impact that extends far beyond the curriculum.

Theme 2: Inconsistent Commitment to Continuous Workplace Cleanliness

Adhering to the "clay-go" or "clean as you go" policy should be a universal standard expected of everyone in any environment, not just schools. This simple principle of properly disposing of one's waste and leaving a space clean after using it is a fundamental aspect of environmental stewardship and personal accountability. However, in schools, many students blatantly disregard this policy, leaving classrooms, hallways, and common areas littered with trash and debris. Discarded food wrappers, drink containers, and other refuse litter surfaces, quickly undoing custodial efforts to maintain cleanliness. This pervasive lack of personal responsibility severely undermines schools' ability to achieve continuous cleanliness standards. Cultivating a culture where the clay-go policy is universally accepted as the baseline expectation and holding individuals accountable is crucial, as failing to implement even this basic tenet findings in unsightly, unsanitary conditions between cleaning cycles. Moreover, research studies have shed light on the alarming disregard for proper waste disposal practices among students in educational settings. According to Okoye (2015), undergraduate students frequently engage in the illicit and improper disposal of waste materials within their institutions, heedless of the potential ramifications for human health and the environment. This behavior demonstrates a lack of environmental consciousness and a disregard for cleanliness standards. Furthermore, Alberto et al. (2020) emphasizes that the principle of "clean as you go," which involves properly disposing of one's waste and leaving spaces tidy after use, should be a universally upheld practice, transcending specific environments. However, many students fail to adhere to this fundamental tenet, contributing to the cycle of uncleanness that custodial staff must continually address. These research findings underscore the need to cultivate a culture of personal accountability and environmental stewardship among the student body to uphold basic cleanliness protocols.

Subtheme 2.1 Cultivating Environmental Stewardship and Accountability in Students

A lack of environmental awareness and personal accountability plagues many students, leading them to disregard proper waste disposal protocols like the "clean as you go" policy. This finding is based on littered campuses and unsanitary conditions. Research highlights the importance of addressing this issue holistically. Syah & Edinov (2019) found student discipline to be a key factor influencing clean behavior and adherence to waste management guidelines. Additionally, Gusti (2016) revealed a relationship between students' knowledge levels and their attitudes towards sustainable waste management practices. To cultivate a culture of environmental stewardship, schools must integrate environmental education across curricula, implement incentive systems for positive behaviors, promote student-led cleanliness initiatives, and encourage collaborative solutions developed by students, faculty, and staff. Tackling both disciplinary aspects and knowledge gaps can foster a generation of environmentally conscious individuals who

take personal responsibility for maintaining clean surroundings.

Theme 3 Disciplinary Measure and Academic Consequences of Inadequate Trash Disposal

In educational settings, maintaining a clean and hygienic environment is essential for fostering a conducive learning environment. However, inadequate trash disposal practices among students pose significant challenges to this endeavor. By examining disciplinary actions taken by educators in response to improper waste management, the researchers aim to understand the implications for student behavior and academic performance. This does not only emphasize the importance of promoting responsible waste management habits among students but also draws attention to the possible consequences for educational institutions. A study by Gouge (2019) found that improper waste management in schools impacts students' concentration and academic performance. Moreover, the study revealed a correlation between the cleanliness of school environments and students' sense of pride and responsibility, highlighting the need for effective waste management strategies to promote positive behavior among students.

Subtheme 3.1 Student Accountability and Responsibility.

This sub-theme focuses on exploring the extent to which students are held accountable for their trash disposal habits and the influence of this accountability on their behavior and academic performance. According to Utami, (2020), they found that students who perceived themselves as accountable for maintaining a clean environment were more likely to adhere to waste management guidelines and engage in responsible disposal practices. Furthermore, the study revealed a positive correlation between students' sense of accountability and their academic performance, suggesting that responsible behavior extends beyond environmental stewardship to encompass broader aspects of student conduct and achievement. In a related study, Mayjaro (2018), investigated the effectiveness of disciplinary measures in promoting accountability among students with regard to waste management. Additionally, educators emphasized the importance of fostering a sense of responsibility among students through positive reinforcement and proactive communication about the consequences of improper waste disposal.

Theme 4: Promoting Responsible Waste Management and Environmental Initiatives

Waste segregation, or the separation of different types of waste at the source, plays a crucial role in responsible waste management and environmental initiatives, particularly in school settings. Proper waste segregation ensures that recyclables, organic waste, and non-recyclables are handled appropriately. Within schools, effective waste segregation practices can have far-reaching impacts on reducing overall waste volume, cultivating environmental awareness, enabling recycling and composting efforts, and influencing the broader community's waste management approach. The potential benefits of improving waste segregation in schools are significant. Schools play a pivotal role in promoting responsible waste management through effective segregation practices. Dedicated bins

for separating recyclables, organic waste, and non-recyclables must be placed strategically across campus.

Moreover, educational initiatives like workshops and activities foster understanding among students about proper segregation and its environmental impact. Involving student-led environmental clubs cultivates ownership and peer learning. Partnering with local waste management stakeholders ensures streamlined collection and processing of segregated waste streams. Regular assessments identify areas for improvement, enabling continuous program optimization. By addressing these key aspects, schools can ingrain sustainable waste segregation habits from an early age. Implementing effective waste segregation in schools involves several key components supported by recent research. Providing proper infrastructure like clearly labeled bins for separating recyclables, organics, and non-recyclables across campus is essential (Kaza et al. 2018). Educational initiatives through workshops and activities raise awareness of segregation's importance. Crucially, "student-led initiatives and peer education are effective in promoting waste segregation practices and instilling a sense of environmental responsibility". Involving student clubs and green teams cultivates ownership and drives engagement. Collaborating with local waste authorities streamlines segregated waste handling. Regular monitoring evaluates program efficacy for continual improvement. By combining infrastructure, education, student leadership, partnerships, and monitoring mechanisms, schools can successfully institutionalize comprehensive waste segregation, as demonstrated by the latest studies.

Subtheme 4.1 Empowering Youth for Sustainable Waste Management

The involvement of young people is crucial in preserving and sustainably managing natural resources. According to Bundhoo, (2018) empowering the youth to embrace responsible waste management and environmental stewardship is essential. By instilling environmental consciousness, knowledge, and individual responsibility, we can nurture a generation committed to safeguarding our planet. Ardoin et al. (2022) emphasize that environmental education goes beyond simply imparting information; it involves enhancing environmental attitudes, awareness, knowledge, and skills to inspire proactive environmental engagement.

Theme 5: Educational Engagement and Behaviors Adjustment About Proper Waste Management

Waste management is a major problem that impacts the environment, human health, and the next generation. The purpose of this research study is to Senior high school students about appropriate waste management techniques. In this study, participants will gain knowledge about the advantages of proper waste handling as well as the consequences of incorrect disposal through engaging in workshops, educational seminars, putting more trash bins, and practical exercises. The goal is to encourage a change in wasteful attitudes and actions. The aim is to make student's future cleaner, greener, and more sustainable. Throughout the educational activity, students will be exposed to a myriad of learning opportunities aimed at broadening their perspectives on waste management.

According to Monegro (2024), Effective recycling is not merely a matter of collecting waste; it also requires meticulous categorization to maximize the potential for reusing material and minimizing waste sent to landfills. Workshops will offer hands-on experiences, allowing students to actively engage with waste sorting, recycling processes, and composting methods. Educational seminars will delve into the environmental and health impacts of improper waste disposal, shedding light on the urgency of adopting sustainable waste management practices. Practical exercises will provide students with the chance to apply their newfound knowledge in real-world scenarios, reinforcing the importance of responsible waste handling.

Subtheme 5.1 Awareness and Knowledge of the 3R's Among the Senior High School Students

Awareness and knowledge of the 3Rs (reduce, reuse, and recycle) among the senior high school students. This sub-theme explores the effects of integrating senior high school student perceptions and attitudes in terms of the 3Rs (reduce, reuse, recycle) and waste segregation education for senior high school students. And examines how the teacher affects the student waste segregation practices and the significant impact on adding senior high school students' drive and motivation towards learning because, according to Ike et al. (2018), educating people through information dissemination on how to handle produced solid waste has become essential.

Conclusions

Based on the study's findings the following conclusions were formulated:

1. This study reveals diverse student attitudes toward waste management. Many students understand its importance and support recycling, but challenges include a need for more awareness and limited recycling facilities. Improving education and accessibility and fostering responsibility can enhance sustainable behaviors on campus.
2. Infrequent breaks for trash disposal hinder senior high school students' consistent practice of the 3Rs (Reduce, Reuse, Recycle) during the school day. Providing structured breaks or designated times for waste disposal could improve adherence to sustainable practices and foster a more environmentally conscious school culture. Addressing these practical challenges is crucial to promoting sustainable behaviors among students.
3. Based on the findings, the researchers conclude that student's express dissatisfaction with the current waste management practices. They observe inconsistencies in trash segregation by waste custodians and note similar issues in the cafeteria. Additionally, students advocate for the introduction of classroom

trash bins and urge teachers to take a more active role in waste management initiatives.

Recommendations

The findings and discussions of this study offer practical and theoretical suggestions for (a) educational practices and (b) forthcoming research endeavors in the field of effective waste management.

1. Students can organize and participate in awareness campaigns within their schools to promote proper waste segregation practices. These campaigns can include informative sessions, posters, and interactive activities to educate their peers about the importance of separating recyclable materials from non-recyclables. Students can take the initiative to establish and maintain recycling programs within their school premises. They can collaborate with school administrators to set up recycling bins in strategic locations and coordinate regular collections. Additionally, students can organize recycling drives to collect recyclable materials from their classmates and ensure they are properly processed for reuse or recycling.
2. Environmental advocates should actively collaborate with educational institutions to develop and implement comprehensive environmental education and awareness programs. These programs should be tailored to address the specific needs and challenges identified in the study, such as enhancing students' knowledge of proper waste management practices, promoting the 3Rs (Reduce, Reuse, and Recycle), and fostering a culture of responsibility towards environmental stewardship. Environmental advocates can leverage their expertise and resources to create engaging and informative educational materials, organize workshops, and provide training for educators. Additionally, they should encourage and support the involvement of student organizations in environmental initiatives, fostering a sense of ownership and empowerment among the student community.
3. Waste custodians can actively demonstrate responsible waste management practices by consistently segregating their trash properly and using designated recycling bins. By being visible proponents of waste segregation, they can also encourage others to adopt similar behaviors through positive reinforcement and by highlighting the environmental benefits of waste segregation.
4. Educational institutions bear a significant responsibility in promoting sustainable waste management practices among them. They should prioritize the implementation of structured break times or designated periods during the school day, allowing students ample opportunity to dispose of their trash properly. This measure directly addresses the identified barrier hindering students' consistent adoption of sustainable practices. Furthermore, institutions should provide adequate and accessible recycling facilities on campus, ensuring that students have convenient options for recycling various materials.
5. Clear labeling and guidance on recycling procedures should be provided to encourage active participation. Institutions should also review and enhance their overall waste

management strategies, addressing concerns raised by students regarding inconsistencies in trash segregation and the lack of classroom trash bins. Regular training and monitoring of janitorial staff, as well as the installation of appropriate waste receptacles in classrooms, could help address these issues

6. Future researchers concentrate on informing school premises about the significance of trash reduction, segregation, and recycling. Additionally, future researchers should collaborate with local businesses to implement sustainable practices and encourage students to participate in community clean-up initiatives, fostering a culture of environmental responsibility both within and beyond the school walls. Future researchers examine the viewpoints of different school community stakeholders, such as students, instructors, administrators, and janitors, in order to learn about their experiences, worries, and recommendations for waste management procedures. In addition to developing methods for sustainable resource management and conservation, research may concentrate on comprehending the effects of environmental degradation on ecosystems and human beings.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research strictly adheres to the ethical standards set by the institution and the body of knowledge. All information and data coming from the respondents are solely for academic purposes only. In line also with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, the researchers strictly preserved the anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents.

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